

Revitalizing Deori Identity: Ethnic Assertion and Heritage Revival under Viksit Bharat 2047

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Abstract: Amartya Sen's approach to identity is plural and constructed, while Darity, Taylor-Simard, Riggs, and Hutchinson-Smith focus on the ethnic ties of ancestry, history, and culture for the survival of indigenous peoples in a globalized world. The Deori, an indigenous people of Assam's plains, an "offspring of gods," are threatened by linguistic extinction beyond the Dibongiya khel, religious changes, and urbanization. The Deori Autonomous Council of 2005 promotes socio-economic, educational, and cultural development through transparent and inclusive policies. Viksit Bharat 2047 opens avenues linking Deori identity assertion to the nation's vision of inclusion, unity, and diversity. Through historical-explanatory methods and data, the study examines ethnic mobilization and proposes revival strategies such as digital archives, bilingual education, and handicraft marketing that integrate with the vision of a developed nation for India by 2047.

Keywords: Deori Identity, Ethnic Assertion, Heritage Revival, Viksit Bharat 2047, Autonomous Council

1. Introduction:

Amartya Sen defines identity as inherently plural and multifaceted phenomenon, rejecting singular affiliations like religion or nationality. He emphasizes the "choice of identities," where individuals actively select and prioritize among multiple, overlapping affiliations rather than being confined to a single one [1]. William A. Darity Jr. describes identity - racial, ethnic, and gender- as positional, based on group power relations and historical dislocation. Indigenous peoples assert it to protect culture, which remains essential for the survival of communities. D.M. Taylor and L.M. Simard describe ethnic identity as a core component of self-definition derived from affiliation with a specific group [2]. In this vein, Fred W. Riggs (1998) observes that globalization heightens ethnic communities' self-awareness relative to others, prompting mobilization to protect and enhance cultural practices within the modern world system, often invoking self-determination and sovereignty. John Hutchinson and Anthony D. Smith define ethnic identity as a shared feeling of belonging to a specific group [3]. This group is connected by common myths of ancestry,

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historical memories, cultural traits like language or religion, ties to a homeland, and solidarity. They highlight that this shared ethnic feeling still plays a major role in how individuals identify themselves today.

However, ethnic groups like Deoris are losing heritage due to linguistic shifts, ritual transformations, and urbanization amid modernization. This indigenous tribes of Assam faces identity crises and cultural erosion. In this scenario, this paper analyses ethnic assertion and heritage revival strategies for the Deori, integrating them with Viksit Bharat 2047's inclusive development goals.

2. Review of Literature:

Bipasha Rosy Lakra (2024) study on 'Tea Tribe' or 'Scheduled Tribe'?: *Vexed Adivasi Identity in Assam*, looks at the struggle of Adivasis for Scheduled Tribe status in Assam, emphasizing the importance of ethnic identity in the inclusive policies of Viksit Bharat@2047. Banasri Hazarika & Tridip Boruah (2025) paper on *the tradition and culture of the Chutiyas tribe of Assam and its changes: A discussion*, studied the cultural transformation of Chutiyas in the context of globalization, promoting the importance of preservation. Dipawoli Kurmi (2023) study on *Preserving Cultural Identity: A study among The Tai Phake Community of Dibrugarh District, Assam*, emphasizes the importance of Tai Phake cultural heritage in promoting inclusion, while Siva Nath Pait (2020), work on *Ethnic Identity Movement Of The Misings Of Assam*, emphasizes Mising ethnic movements for cultural independence and national integration. These studies show that preserving ethnic group identities is key to achieving inclusive, diverse development by 2047.

3. Objective of the Paper:

The paper examines ethnic assertion and heritage revival strategies for the Deori community, integrating them with Viksit Bharat@2047's inclusive development objectives.

4. Methodology:

The researcher uses both historical and explanatory methodologies to achieve the objective of the study. Primary and secondary data were gathered from various sources, supplemented by the investigator's insights to reach conclusions.

5. The Viksit Bharat@2047 and Deori Identity:

Viksit Bharat@2047 has a vision of a developed India in the 2047 centenary celebrations of independence, which focuses on economic development, sustainability, youth empowerment, and the revival of Indian

Knowledge Systems. The special emphasis on cultural revival brings ethnic traditional practices into focus. In 2025, the Ministry of Culture launched a five-pillar approach to make India a cultural superpower: preservation of heritage, democratization of access, leveraging technology, promoting the creative economy, and Vishwabandhu diplomacy. This approach is inclusive and provides the Deori an opportunity to move from passive preservation to active revival of their culture.

6. Historical Context of Ethnic Assertion of Deoris:

6.1 Who are the Deori people:

The Deori community is an indigenous plains tribe of Assam, belonging to the Tibeto-Burman community, speaking a language of the same family. "Deori" means "offsprings of gods," with "De" indicating great or wise, and "O/Ri" indicating male/female; some linguists, such as B.K. Kakati, connect it to "deva-grhika" in Sanskrit. A Deori Language Dictionary to Assamese and English by Radha Kanta Deori states that Deoris are an aboriginal tribe of Assam, characterized by their distinct language, religion, culture, customs, and lifestyle [4].

6.2 Historical Role:

Edward Gait refers Deoris as priests of Chutiya kings at Sadiya, worshipping Tamreswari (Kechaikhati) and Baliababa[5]. W.B. Brown refers them as the Levite class among Chutiyas, who were originally beyond Sadiya, migrating westwards a century ago through rivers Dibong, Tengapani, and Patarsal to Lakhimpur [6]. Further, the Hemkosh Assamese Dictionary defines Deoris as temple servants who provide divine prasadas to the gods [7].

6.3 Subgroups and Migration:

Dalton writes about the Deoris: "An isolated colony on the Dikrong River in Lakhimpur, calling themselves Deori Chutia, was found; they spoke a peculiar language termed Chutiya and were known as Deoris"[8]. During the early Ahom period, kings held Deoris in high esteem, with the administration maintaining constant vigilance over their safety and security. The Deoris are divided into four khels: Dibongiya, Barganya, Tengapania, and Patarganya, and they were respected as subgroups during the Ahom period, with current residences in the riverine districts of Lakhimpur, Dibrugarh, Sivasagar, Jorhat, and Sonitpur.

6.4 History of Deori Identity Movement:

The ethnic awareness of the Deori community began during the colonial period but accelerated after the independence of India. Bhimbor Deori, an important nationalist, organized the community through culture, customs, and language; he was the leader of the Tribal League during the visit of the Simon Commission in 1928 and formed the Assam Plain Tribal League as General Secretary in 1933, demanding land pattas for the native Assamese. In 1935, he formed Deori Janagosthi Ganatantik Yakhya Mancha (Deori Sanmilan) for the protection of Deori identity. After 1951, there were Deori Satra Sanmilani (February 12, 1951, Lakhimpur) for cultural protection and relief from backwardness, All Assam Deori Students' Union (1959), Deori Sahitya Sabha (January 20, 1965), and more recently, organizations such as All Assam Deori Autonomous Demand Committee (1994), Nikhil Bharat Deori Yuba-Satra Santha, Sado Deori Mahila Samiti, Deori Sanskriti Sangha, and Sadou Asom Deori Haseton Nagarik Yuba Manch.

6.4.1 Key Demands of Deori Organizations

Deori organizations demand increased autonomy and recognition:

Table: 6.1 Nature of demands and special requests of Deoris

Nature of Demand	Special Requests
Autonomy	Separate Greater Deori Autonomy; 3-tier satellite system (village, regional, state council levels) in TSP areas and Deori villages.
Protection and Promotion of Language & Enhanced Educational Opportunities	Official recognition of Deori language; inclusion in primary schools with teachers; hostels for higher education, especially girls.
Cultural Recognition	Holiday for Deori Bohag Bisu (1st Wednesday of Bohag Month); restoration of Kundil Nagar monuments and temples.
Land Rights Protection and Community Welfare	Land pattas distribution; Bhimbar Deori Memorial Hospital in Lakhimpur; research funding for Dibrugarh University ABILAC (Guwahati).
Protection of Political Rights	Create Second Chamber in Assam; ST (Hills) status for Arunachali Deoris under the Constitution of India.

6.4.2 Outcome and Ongoing Concerns:

The Deori leaders mobilized the community against political neglect, with demands sometimes turning into unrest. The Deori Accord of March 4, 2005, formalized in a Memorandum of Understanding between the Assam Government in presence of former Chief Minister Tarun Gogoi and the Government officials on the one hand and the authorised representatives of Deori leaders on the other hand, resulted in the formation of the Deori Autonomous Council as per Assam Act No. XXV of 2005, enabling the community to govern itself for social, economic, and cultural development. This is still a historic achievement, but the aspirations of ethnic identity are still developing in the face of modern challenges.

7. Key strategies for Identity Preservation of Deoris:

7.1 Digital Cultural Repository:

The Deoris' socio-cultural and religious identity, represented by riverine settlements, Chang ghar houses, Jakarua Jupa (joint families) system, presence of Gaonbura and priestly ranks, clan-specific Midi rituals and recitations (Dibangiya, Tengapaniya, Borgoyans, Patorgonya), requires the digital archiving of folk songs, dances, stories, festivals, oral traditions, and sacrificial rituals. Establishing a digital resource accessible worldwide will provide global coverage, prevent the degradation of intangible heritage, and facilitate intergenerational transmission.

7.2 Language Preservation & Education:

Deoris have an "ancient and rich linguistic heritage" with "distinct dialects" and a strong folklore tradition. Nevertheless, the traditional language is "maintained only in Dibongia khel of Deoris, while the rest of the khels have lost their linguistic identity." Recording and teaching (bilingual education) the Deori language will be a success in resisting assimilation pressures and to maintain oral traditions.

7.3 Creative Economy Promotion:

Apart from agriculture and government sector employment, Deori handloom (Baiga, Egu) and craft, unique and meaningful clothing with special embroideries, can be developed as a luxury brand. Temple markets and festivals provide employment opportunities. Sustainable herbal businesses are also a good source of employment.

7.4 Youth Engagement & Skill Development:

The youth of the Deori community play an important role in maintaining their cultural identity. Through the development of digital platforms and cultural festivals, they can participate in heritage activities. Workshops and seminars will train young Deori priests for the next generation while instilling a multidimensional entrepreneurial spirit. The training of Deori youth as cultural ambassadors and certified heritage guides would be a valuable initiative.

7.5 Women's Empowerment Initiatives:

The Deori women are an integral part of the socio-economic and religious activities of the family. They are more hardworking than men and are skilled in handling the activities of weaving, herb preparation, and Suze (rice beer) production. They are also valued as partners in the open-minded Deori society, and immediate steps are required for women's empowerment to thrive in the changing modern scenario.

7.6 Ethnobotanical Knowledge Documentation:

The traditional Deori herbal medicine has been an important healthcare system since ancient times. The use of local plants has been done for medicinal, dietary and cultural purposes. With the increasing interest in natural medicines and sustainable healthcare systems around the world, there is scope for research in these areas.

7.7 Eco-Spiritual Tourism Development:

Eco-tourism provides an important opportunity for the conservation of Deori identity. The promotion of Than (sacred groves) as spiritual, ecological, and heritage sites can provide sustainable livelihoods for Deori youth as cultural guardians. The periodical community festivals further provide an important opportunity for the spread of their culture and ensure sustainable development.

7.8 Handicraft & Material Culture Revival:

Deoris are professionally skilled in handicrafts. The males are expert in making bamboo and cane products such as baskets, mats, trays (doko, sora), domestic tools, and religious items. The females are skilled in handloom (Puma-gema) weaving Baiga, Egu, Riha, and scarves (takaya) with endi, muga, and pat silk fabrics and exclusive floral designs. Workshop, adequate training, markets, and digital platforms are required to preserve these techniques.

7.9 Indian Knowledge System Integration

The Deori tribe has a rich tradition of herbal medicine, rituals, crafts, and ecology, which has made a significant contribution to Indian Knowledge Systems. The Deori tribe's knowledge of ethnobotany is an excellent example of how healthcare, nutrition, and cultural practices are interwoven; the Than groves help with biodiversity conservation; and the priestly rituals (Deodhoni) are a reflection of spiritual knowledge. Adding oral traditions, weaving practices, and Suze (rice beer) preparation to university courses on IKS will give credence to traditional ecological knowledge as indigenous science.

8. Institutional Governance and DAC Policy:

The Deori Autonomous Council (2005) emerged as a result of the long-standing political demand of Deoris for preserving their identity. They aim at preserving their culture, promoting their language, and improving socio-economic-political backwardness. However, expectations for comprehensive development are still a big question. Deoris are now demanding Sixth Schedule status for overall development in Assam. Therefore, DAC needs to modify policies for socio-economic, educational, and cultural development through e-governance to address these challenges.

9. Conclusion:

Historically known as Jimochayan ("children of the sun and moon") the Deoris have retained a distinct cultural identity since ancient times. However, globalization has eroded this identity, much like in other tribal communities. Notably, the Government of India has initiated special programs to conserve the cultural heritage of these indigenous communities to realize the dream of Viksit Bharat by 2047. This provides the Deoris an opportunity to re-assert their identity and protect their heritage under this mission. However, success will depend on linking their cultural heritage to Viksit Bharat@2047's goals of inclusion, diversity, and harmony, as well as the community's ability to negotiate modernity.

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